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The Lived Experiences of Barbecue Stick Makers: A Phenomenological Inquiry

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Abstract

This phenomenological study reveals the lived experiences of bamboo barbecue stick makers in Montehermoso, Carmen, Bohol, Philippines, exploring their multifaceted realities shaped by economic necessity, physical labor, and aspirations for familial and community support. The research uncovers the intricate web of challenges and aspirations inherent in this informal livelihood through purposive sampling and semi-structured interviews. Key themes emerged, highlighting the critical role of barbecue stick production in supporting daily living and educational aspirations, despite enduring physical strain, occupational hazards, and seasonal constraints. Participants express a resilient commitment to their craft, emphasizing the importance of community solidarity and technological advancements in enhancing productivity and socio-economic well-being. This study contributes to a deeper understanding of informal livelihoods in rural settings, advocating for targeted interventions to support economic resilience, occupational safety, and sustainable livelihoods.

Keywords: *barbecue stick makers, lived experiences, no poverty, decent work and economic growth*

Introduction

Bamboo has long been a versatile and renewable material used in various industries, including the production of barbecue sticks. In the article "Sustainable Bamboo Barbecue Stick Production: Challenges and Opportunities," Chen and Wang (as cited by Marsh & Smith, 2007), provide valuable insights into the sustainability aspects of this industry, highlighting both the challenges and opportunities faced by producers. Making barbecue sticks is a key part of many culinary traditions worldwide and is often considered a traditional craft. Although the process of crafting a skewer to hold meats and vegetables over an open flame may seem straightforward, it is a complex one, shaped by the hands, experiences, and cultural backgrounds of those who create it.

However, scholarly discourse has largely overlooked the lived experiences, craft processes, and meanings associated with the work of barbecue stick producers. Bamboo's ecological requirements and its role in household subsistence economies are crucial considerations for sustainable production (Moktan et al., 2009). The domestication and cultivation of bamboo, along with an understanding of harvesting and regeneration techniques, are essential for the industry's long-term viability. Additionally, socio-economic factors influencing bamboo weaving enterprises and the importance of sustainable forest management practices cannot be overlooked (Yuniati & Khotimah, 2018; Silva et al., 2020; Marsh & Smith, 2007).

Existing research has underscored the importance of understanding the everyday practices and knowledge of food producers and preparers, which can inform community-driven efforts to build knowledge and envision alternatives to top-down production modes (Kuznetsov et al., 2016). These insights highlight the need to elevate the perspectives of barbecue stick producers and to understand the multifaceted meanings and experiences associated with this craft. Opportunities and challenges across the sub-sectors of industrial bamboo, handicrafts, and bamboo shoots further underscore the need for a holistic approach to sustainable bamboo utilization (Yuniati & Khotimah, 2018; Moktan et al., 2009; Silva et al., 2020; Marsh & Smith, 2007).

The industrialization of craft production has also been a focus of research, emphasizing the complex interplay of stakeholders and the role of different forms of capital in shaping the production and consumption of artisanal goods. This study aims to build on these insights by exploring the subjective experiences and perceptions of barbecue stick producers, shedding light on the cultural, social, and economic value of their craft.

Research Questions

The researchers aim to explore the lived experiences and challenges of bamboo stick makers. Their sacrifice and resilience for family education support. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the challenges encountered by barbecue stick makers face in their everyday lives?
2. What are the motivations of barbecue stick makers in their work?
3. What insights and suggestions can be drawn from the experiences of barbecue stick makers?

Literature Review

The study highlighted two key themes: the lived experiences and challenges of bamboo stick makers and the sacrifice and resilience for family education support. It focused on the sustainability aspects of bamboo barbecue stick production, examining both the challenges faced by producers in maintaining sustainability and the opportunities for improving sustainability practices in the industry (Chen, Y., & Wang, L., 2020).

Moreover, Wang, Z., & Liu, S. (2016) examined bamboo barbecue stick production as a livelihood strategy in Southeast Asia, presenting case studies to illustrate how individuals and communities rely on this craft for income generation. The study explores on socio-economic aspects of bamboo barbecue stick production in the region. The study offers offers insights into the role of bamboo barbecue stick production as a livelihood strategy and sheds light on the socio-economic implications of this activity in Southeast Asia. It contributes valuable knowledge to the field of rural studies and economic development in the region. Consequently, Huang, C., & Chen, W. (2019) delved into the traditional techniques of bamboo barbecue stick crafting while also exploring contemporary innovations in the field. It may discuss the cultural significance of bamboo barbecue sticks and how modern advancements have impacted the production process. The study also provided insights into the rich history, cultural significance, and evolving practices of bamboo barbecue stick crafting. It bridges the gap between traditional techniques and contemporary innovations in this craft, offering valuable knowledge to the culinary arts and technology field.

Additionally, Lin, H., & Wu, J. (2018) explored the cultural significance of bamboo barbecue stick crafting in Taiwan, shedding light on traditional practices passed down through generations. It also discussed technological advancements that have influenced the production process in Taiwan. It provides valuable insights into the cultural significance and technological advancements of bamboo barbecue stick crafting in Taiwan.

By combining a focus on tradition with a consideration of modern innovations, the research contributes to a deeper understanding of this craft and its evolution in the Taiwanese context. The effect of the experiences and challenges of bamboo stick makers affirmed that they really sacrifice a lot and endure resilience for their aspirations in life and family education support. Hence, the study offered a comprehensive exploration of the traditional techniques and modern adaptations in bamboo barbecue stick crafting (Zhang, X., & Li, M., 2017). The traditional techniques used in bamboo barbecue stick crafting while also exploring modern adaptations and innovations in the industry can help the bamboo barbecue stick makers to evolve in their making process. The research provides valuable insights into the soci-economic conditions of barbecue stick makers and evolution of bamboo crafts.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employs a qualitative research design grounded in phenomenology to explore the lived experiences of bamboo stick makers. Phenomenology seeks to understand the essence of human experiences as they are lived and perceived by individuals, making it suitable for uncovering the intricate nuances of bamboo stick making. Phenomenological approach designs to explore the lived experiences of barbecue stick makers in the context of supporting their families' educational aspirations. This approach sought to uncover the meanings, beliefs, and values that shape the participants' experiences. As to the study of Iser (1974) phenomenological approach allows for an in-depth examination of the subjective experiences and meanings attributed to these experiences by individuals.

Participants

Participants from Hermoso, Carmen, Bohol, Philippines are selected purposefully to ensure representation from diverse backgrounds and experiences within the barbecue stick maker community. Criteria for selection included varying levels of income, age, gender, educational attainment, employment status, family sizes, geographic locations, and educational aspirations for their children. The research involved interviewing the lived experiences of bamboo barbecue stick makers to gain a concrete understanding of their experiences and perspectives. The purposive sampling approach was used to recruit participants, and semi-structured interviews held with each participant (McIntosh & Morse, 2015).

Instrument

The researchers utilize an interview guide as an important research instrument in a phenomenological study. Data from an focused group discussion were collected through semi-structured questionnaire. The open-ended questions from the tool allowed the participants to share their experiences, challenges, and aspirations in relation to their job as barbecue stick makers. The guide was flexible enough for probing and follow-up questions.

Data Analysis

The study used focused group discussion in gathering data where interviews with open-ended questions were asked to the participant. Thematic analysis was employed to analyze the interview data and identify recurring themes and patterns related to lived experiences of the barbecue stick makers. The gathered data were then subjected to the coding process where codes, categories, and themes were generated following Creswell's mode of data analysis. The emerging themes were then discussed and interpreted.

Ethical Considerations

Prior to participation, participants were provided with informed consent forms outlining the purpose of the study, their rights as participants, and confidentiality measures. Participant confidentiality will be strictly maintained, with all data anonymized and stored securely. It was mentioned during the signing of the consent that data from the interview will be deleted as soon as the findings have been finalized by an inter-coder and checked by a member from the participants. Member's checking was conducted with peers, and

representatives from participants to critically review the research process and findings, enhancing the credibility and rigor of the study. The rigorous methodology provides a comprehensive understanding of the sacrifice and resilience exhibited by barbecue stick makers in supporting their families' educational aspirations, shedding light on their lived experiences within the context of economic struggle and community support.

Results and Discussion

Theme 1: Financial Strain

Barbecue stick making serves as a crucial source of income for participants, enabling them to address immediate financial needs and fulfill long-term financial responsibilities such as education expenses. T2 explained that:

T2: “carrying, cutting, and slicing the bamboo is difficult but I need it to pay the students’ tuition fee and allowance. Every week our income is less than 700 pesos and when we do overtime we earned 200 pesos”

The demanding nature of the work, particularly in bamboo cutting and slicing, highlights the physical challenges faced by the participants. Despite the difficulty, the motivation to meet educational expenses for their children underscores the strong familial commitment that drives them to continue in this labor-intensive job. The income, though modest, plays a vital role in sustaining household needs, indicating that even small earnings can be crucial in contexts where financial margins are thin. This resonates with findings by García-Gómez & Villar (2021) and Gomber et al. (2019), emphasizing that such labor, while physically strenuous, remains an essential lifeline for families struggling with financial constraints.

Theme 2: Physical Risk and Danger

The personal accounts of T2 and T3 reveal the dangerous conditions under which participants perform their labor, emphasizing the physical risks inherent in bamboo stick making.

T2: “there’s a time that my eyes almost hit when I get the bamboo, get wounded during the process of making the bamboo stick.”

T3: “carry the bamboo on my shoulder, sacrificing despite of the heat of the sun- I still saw the bamboo even though I’m pregnant. My worst experience that I cannot forget is that my right eye was accidentally hit by the bamboo tree when I cut it.”

T2’s experience of nearly injuring their eyes and sustaining wounds during the process illustrates the immediate dangers that arise from handling sharp tools and heavy materials. T3’s narrative of carrying bamboo under the harsh sun while pregnant further underscores the extreme physical toll and lack of accommodation for vulnerable workers. These examples highlight the broader issue of inadequate occupational safety and the need for interventions that protect workers from preventable injuries. The data aligns with research by Bambra et al. (2020) and Lee & Lee (2019), who stress the importance of integrating health and safety measures into labor-intensive industries to enhance well-being and productivity.

Theme 3: Family Support and Educational Aspiration

Family plays a central role in participants' livelihood strategies and decision-making processes.

T2: “this job is so important to me because my child finished college education.”

T3: “my income really help my college, high school and elementary student for their Allowances”

T5: “ I can earn and save money for my children for their college studies and get a brighter future someday”

The participants’ statements illustrate the deep connection between their labor and their aspirations for their children's education and future success. T2 emphasizes how their work directly contributed to their child’s completion of a college education, underlining the sense of fulfillment and purpose that comes from providing educational opportunities. T3’s and T5’s comments further reflect the pivotal role of their income in supporting their children’s academic journeys, from elementary to college levels. These narratives highlight how education is perceived as a crucial pathway to a better future, not just for the individual students but for the entire family. The parents’ dedication to saving for their children's education demonstrates their long-term focus on securing socio-economic mobility and breaking the cycle of poverty. This aligns with the findings of Chakraborty (2021) and Lee (2019), who discuss the vital role of parental support and education in fostering upward mobility and transforming communities. By gaining a quality education, young people receive the necessary training to make informed decisions and grow into productive citizens who can actively contribute to the nation’s progress and development. Even for barbecue stick makers, ensuring their children’s education is seen as a pathway to equip them with the skills and knowledge needed to secure a better future and uplift their families and communities (Ampo, 2023).

Theme 4: Aspirations for Technological Advancement and Government Support:

The responses from participants, as shown in quotes T5 and T6, reflect a strong desire for technological interventions that can ease their labor-intensive work and increase their economic output.

T5: “All I want is to have a machine to make easier and have a better production and earn more money.”

T6: “We are very hopeful that the government will help us through giving us machine for the production of barbeque sticks. With this, it makes our job easier and earn more income.”

These responses align with the broader theme that emphasizes the need for structural interventions, particularly those that address systemic barriers to socio-economic progress. Participants express a clear understanding that technological innovations, such as machines for production, would significantly enhance their productivity and income. This indicates that, for them, access to modern tools and technology is directly linked to improving their livelihoods.

The hope for government support, expressed in T6, suggests that participants see public policy and government intervention as crucial in providing access to these innovations. It underscores the role of government in facilitating inclusive economic development, particularly in marginalized communities. This is consistent with findings from studies like Bettencourt et al. (2021) and Breunig et al. (2021), which discuss the importance of public policy in promoting economic opportunities and ensuring the well-being of disadvantaged groups.

The participants' desires for improved production methods and increased income further suggest that structural changes, such as the provision of appropriate technologies, can be an effective strategy for lifting marginalized groups out of poverty. These interventions not only improve immediate working conditions but also contribute to broader goals of sustainable economic growth and long-term socio-economic resilience. The responses imply that policy measures and technological support must work in tandem to remove systemic barriers and foster more inclusive economic advancement.

Conclusions

Barbecue stick makers are an underserved and unrepresented group in society. Living in marginalized communities, they struggle daily for survival. The risks they face in making barbecue sticks often do not adequately meet their basic needs. However, their resilience in the face of daily adversity is incomparable. Despite being underserved, their overall contribution to our economy is highly significant.

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